

A NOTE ON THE KEEPING PROPERTIES OF *HYDNOCARPUS WIGHTIANA* OIL AND ITS DERIVATIVES.

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It has been recently shown by us (*Leprosy in India*, 1939, **11**, 53) that the addition of creosote (4%), or hydroquinone (0.02%) inhibits the autooxidation and markedly improves the keeping properties of *Hydnocarpus Wightiana* oil as well as the iodized ethyl esters of the acids derived from this oil. This retarding effect of creosote has now been observed at still a lower concentration (0.1-0.2%). The oil contains an unsaponifiable substance (about 0.02%), which is, however, not pro-oxygenic in nature.

A concentrate, prepared by a slight modification of the method of Green and Hilditch (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1937, **56**, 23 r), from the oil cake of the *Hydnocarpus Wightiana*, dissolved in sodium bicarbonate, reduced Fehling's solutions and showed the presence of nitrogen and was insoluble in ether but possessed no appreciable anti-oxygenic power. A similar concentrate prepared from sesame oil cake, however, possessed a considerable antioxygenic activity. Thus, the peroxide value 63.8 (in terms of 0.01 N-thio.), obtained by heating an oil at 100° for about 4½ hours was reduced to about 2.6 when the oil was mixed with 0.5% concentrate from the latter cake. This concentrate is very rich in nitrogen (6.1%), and also insoluble in petrol ether. Further work in this direction is in progress.

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